

Wiring the Second World: The Geopolitics of Information and Communications Technology in Post-Totalitarian Eurasia

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Control of information is the first prerequisite of any totalitarian society; while in authoritarian systems, it is simply a perquisite afforded the state. During the past two decades, the residents of the Second World—the vast geopolitical bloc that stretched from Poznań to Pyongyang and Noril'sk to Namangan—have experienced both totalitarian and authoritarian control of information. Some have even been lucky enough to taste a free flow of data, images, music, and ideas via the rapidly evolving suite of information and communications technologies (ICTs) and new media. In this essay, I explore the history of “wiring” the Second World, as well as current trends in ICT deployment, the cultural penetration of new media, and the impact of both on the larger political environment in post-totalitarian Eurasia.

While the term “Second World” has fallen into disuse in recent years, it remains a helpful concept for distinguishing post-totalitarian Eurasian states from the mature market economies of the West *and* the underdeveloped, quasi-states of Latin America, Africa, and Asia. The term itself is derivative, gleaned from French demographer Alfred Sauvy's 1952 article in *L'Observateur* in which he described a global struggle between the West and the Soviet bloc for control of an “ignored, exploited, and misunderstood” Third World (c.f. Mason 1997, 30). In his use of “Third World,” Sauvy inadvertently provided political pundits with convenient shorthand to refer both to the capitalist “West” (the First World) and the Communist “East” (the Second World). While the First World later came to include Japan, Hong Kong, South Korea, and other developed economies, the Second World remained remarkably static from the 1950s until the first fractures appeared in the late 1980s. Since the abolition of the one-party state in Eastern Europe (1989) and the Soviet republics (1990-1991) and China's dramatic socio-economic transformation since 1978, the unity—both in terms of ideology and economics—of the Second World has splintered. Despite this, there is still value in conceptualising a world between the conceptual extremes of “First World” Luxembourg and “Third World” Lesotho. According to geopolitician Parag Khanna, “Second-world countries are frequently *both* first- and third-world countries at the same time. In second-world societies, some percentage of the population lives a modern lifestyle—globally connected with reliable high-wage employment—but coexists with a narrow middle class and the mass of the poor” (Khanna 2008, xxv). While I do not contend that the Second World moniker is the only (not

perhaps even the best) description of post-totalitarian Eurasia, it does offer a good starting point for understanding the seminal role of new media and ICTs in twenty-first century geopolitics.

Today, nearly every country that comprised the so-called “Communist Bloc” (with the notable exception of North Korea) is clamouring to strengthen its position in the global economy through increasing the depth and sophistication of its ICT infrastructure.¹ But while nearly these states throatily espouse their embrace of informatization, defined as “the process primarily by which information technologies, such as the world-wide web and other communication technologies, have transformed economic and social relations to such an extent that cultural and economic barriers are minimized” (Kluver, 2000), the genuine level of informational freedom in these various republics ranges dramatically. Even if we confine our analysis to post-Soviet states, we see huge divergence. One the one end of the spectrum, we find “Estonia,” a liberal, plural democracy which places higher in media freedom rankings than either Great Britain or Australia and leads the world in transitioning to e-government; at the other end, there is totalitarian Turkmenistan, a country where media freedom is non-existent and which only began to allow private citizens to access the Internet in mid-2008.²

When we expand our gaze beyond post-Soviet space to the rest of the Second World, a curious host of disparities come into focus. Albania—a Mediterranean country that borders the European Union—lags in Internet connectivity with barely one-tenth of its population online, while China—a nation which exhibited Third World characteristics as recently as the late 1970s—is the world leader in terms of Internet users (estimated at 253 million in 2007, easily surpassing the United States’ 215 million, though China lags in terms of Internet penetration at 20% compared to the American rate of 70%). As such, it is clear that there is no simple explanation for the current state of new media penetration in the Second World. One must look deeper to understand why Shanghai, St. Petersburg, and Split bristle with cyber-café, mobile phone users, and hipster digerati, while Tirana, Tyumen’, and Tashkent languish in virtual cul-de-sacs far from the information superhighway. In order to do this, we must trace both the history of the Internet *and* nineteenth century flows of goods and people which established insoluble corridors information transmission. In doing so, it becomes clear that certain Second World states benefited from path dependency as they moved towards the global information age.

During the last quarter of the twentieth century, the Soviet, Eastern European, and Chinese Communist Parties grappled with challenges posed by the global shift towards free-flowing information, computerized workplaces, and the spread of personal communications technologies. In much of the Second World, the communications and media delivery infra-

¹ In the use of this term “Communist Bloc,” I do not restrict myself to the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics and its allies (the People’s Republics of Bulgaria, Poland, Romania, Mongolia, and Hungary, the German Democratic Republic, the Socialist Republic of Czechoslovakia, the People’s Democratic Republic of Korea, and Vietnam), but also include Communist rivals (and estranged allies) of the USSR, such as the People’s Republic of China, the People’s Socialist Republic of Albania, and the Federal People’s Republic of Yugoslavia. The scope of this essay is confined to the contiguous band of 31 formerly (or current) one-party, Marxist-Leninist states on the super-continent of Eurasia; as a result, I have not included any discussion of peripheral countries (e.g., Yemen, Cuba, and Ethiopia) which might otherwise be described as “Second World.” The focus of this essay, however, is predominately on the former USSR.

² In Reporters without Borders’ 2007 World Press Freedom Index, Estonia tied for third place, topped only by Iceland and Norway; Turkmenistan ranked 167 out of 169 countries.

structures had been built on an autocratic (tsarist Russia and Qing China) backbone.³ Later, the totalitarian necessity to maintain control of information flows precluded the deployment of one-to-one networks, such as the personal telephone, which had flourished in the market-driven societies of the West. Instead of wiring individual apartments and homes with telephones, the government invested in loud speaker systems that could broadcast information to the village square, community centre, or street corner. One-to-many became the default methodology for information transmission in the Second World. Beyond the pale of politics, Stalinist economics, which regarded all expenditures that did not result in measurable production as cost centres for the economy, also retarded investment telecommunications infrastructure (Franda 2002, 130).

In terms of media outlets, party monopolies on the printed word were buttressed by the developing platforms of the motion picture, radio broadcasts, and finally television (Price 1995). While Lenin initially criticized the capitalist nature of the film-making industry, the state turned the allure of the movie theatre to its own didactic advantage under the New Economic Policy (1921-29). Lenin later declared that cinema was, for the current epoch, the “most important of the arts” (Lunacharsky 1926). Through subsidies drawn from the showing of foreign films, Moscow quickly developed an indigenous motion picture industry based on the principles of agitprop, aimed at wooing Russians from their addictions to the Church and vodka (Rimberg 1973). Like loud speakers, the movie theatre offered the Communist Party a vehicle to broadcast one-way communications to the masses. Likewise, radio—a technology which exploded during the interwar period—became a powerful tool for propaganda. In an environment where the government wielded influence over radio broadcasts, the platform quickly became a tool of mental control, effectively marginalising the “ideas and opinions of minority groups which [might] disturb or unsettle the minds of mass listeners” (Riegel 1938, 514). In post-World War II Eastern Europe, the control of radio transmissions allowed local Communist parties—which virtually controlled the ministries of information—to manipulate elections, dominate the public sphere, and prepare the way for the imposition of totalitarianism in 1947 and 1948. Such extension of power via media technologies provides support to Friedrich Kittler’s argument modern media are “suffused with war” and the each new advance is simply a “strategic escalation” of extant conflict (1999, xxxvi).

During the early Khrushchev era, television was added to the repertoire of Soviet propaganda tools; however, it was not until the 1960s and 1970s that the platform gained a mass audience (Mickiewicz 1981). Due to technological hurdles, the ability to deliver uniform content to all locations within the USSR suffered in the early days of television. However, this impediment was soon removed. The lead in the space race serendipitously assisted the USSR in its deployment of state-centric ICT. In 1967, the Soviet Union launched its *Orbita* (‘Orbit’) satellite network to deliver television to its domestic market guaranteeing that almost every Soviet citizen—whether in the Kola Peninsula or Kamchatka—would have access to state broadcasts of news, information, and entertainment. The USSR thus became the first

³ This is less true in Europe west of the thirtieth meridian east (the approximate border between Soviet Russia and the rest of Europe). German and Austro-Hungarian communications infrastructures were comparatively more egalitarian in form, as were the telecommunications build-outs of interwar Eastern European states from the Baltic to the Black Sea. In fact, Estonia was a leader in radio engineering during the 1930s laying the groundwork for future innovation in mobile telecommunications (see Högselius 2005: 286).

country to deploy ubiquitous television programming via space-based technologies. Just over a decade later, Moscow again led the world with the first nationally-available direct-to-home satellite broadcasting system, *Ekran* ('Screen'). Unlike the U.S. and Western Europe where private satellite programming flourished in the late 1970s, "Programming content was monitored by the KGB, and the military and defence ministries controlled the development, allocation, launch, and uses of communications satellites" (Glanley 1996, 5). However, the launch of *Orbita* and its successor *Ekran* were Pyrrhic victories for Moscow as the advent of satellite television marked a new era of freer and deterritorialized media production and consumption. The interconnected world of satellite beams, optical cables, and wireless transmissions long predicted by science fiction writers from H.G. Wells to Arthur C. Clarke was starting to come true. Satellite television—rather than representing the apotheosis of totalitarian information control—heralded the coming of the "global village" prophesied in Marshall McLuhan's *The Gutenberg Galaxy: The Making of Typographic Man* (1962).

In late 1970s, the First World began to move towards informational, financial, and—to a lesser extent—cultural interdependency. The introduction of computers, personal telephones, and fax machines into the workforce which accompanied post-industrialism initiated an ideological quandary for totalitarian countries like the USSR and Maoist China. Should they embrace these new technologies and risk opening up their systems to external influence and the free flow of information? Or would it be better to keep the effects of globalization and interdependence at bay? Japan, the United States, Germany and other Western European countries rapidly transitioned from a focus on heavy industry towards becoming "information societies." Conversely, the USSR and its socialist allies effectively sealed themselves off from this development, continuing to pursue industrial development without employing advances in information technology. Nikita Khrushchev's predictions of the USSR surpassing the developed economies of the West crumbled in the last quarter of the twentieth century as European, North American, and capitalist East Asian economies digitized the workplace. As the fateful decade of the 1980s dawned, those socialist countries which refused to remake themselves into "knowledge economies" and embrace the benefits of high technology lagged farther behind.⁴ While mass deployment of ICTs was welcomed in the information-centric societies of North America, Western Europe, and the rest of the First world, such social change was anathema to the closed societies of the Second World where typewriters were registered with the secret police, fax machines were potential enemies of the state, and Xerox was a dirty word. Under Moscow's tutelage, it might have been assumed that the "captive nations" of Eastern Europe would toe the line on ICTs, but long before the ascendancy of Mikhail Gorbachev, the people's republics began experimenting with increasingly open communications and information regimes. Hungary's "goulash Communism" and the residual effects of Bonn's *Ostpolitik* ('Eastern Politics') on the DDR helped pry open the hermetically-sealed ICT and media infrastructures of the Eastern Bloc.

On the fringes of the Second World, the flood of texts and transmissions could barely be kept at bay: Estonians listened to Swedish news broadcasts, Latvians hoarded British punk records, Croats watched Italian game shows, and Poles clung on every word of "their" Pope

⁴ A case in point is Poland, which had been the tenth largest economy in the world and had a rate of growth nearly equal to Japan's in the early 1970s before nearly going bankrupt in the 1980s.

in Rome. The trans-regional pathways of information, embedded in Europe during the late medieval and early modern periods, remained eerily solvent despite the best efforts of paranoid party officials to quash them under the treads of Moscow's new world order of "socialist fraternity." Such examples included the resilience of a common Baltic cultural space, London-Poland familial bonds, and social networks which continued to link the regional capital of the long-dead Habsburg Empire. Similar changes were afoot in the far eastern fringes of the Second World. In order to ensure that China was not left behind in the IT revolution (as it had been by the industrial revolution of the nineteenth century), Beijing actively backed wiring—literally and figuratively—the country's economy to the outside world, while carefully policing the "red lines" of political discourse (see Tai 2006). Under Deng Xiaoping, the People's Republic of China (PRC) steadily emerged from Maoist isolation and totalitarianism and laid the groundwork for "rising dragon." The hothouse for this radical change proved to be Shanghai (Europe's old foothold in imperial China) and Guangdong and Fujian (the hinterlands of Hong Kong and Macau, the traditional entrepôts of European goods, people, and ideas).

By the mid-1980s, informational freedom and spread of ICT seemed to be proving geopolitician Nicholas Spykman's theory of the "Rimland" to be true. Countering English geographer Halford Mackinder's contention that "Who rules East Europe commands the Heartland; Who rules the Heartland commands the World-Island; Who rules the World-Island commands the World" (Mackinder 1919 [1942], 106), Spykman argued in *The Geography of the Peace* (1944) that sea power (commanded by the British, the Japanese, and ultimately the Americans) trumped land-based imperial projects. Spykman posited that the new world order forged during Europe's imperial expansion had paradoxically turned the old centre (the "heartland" of the world island) into the periphery. The old oases of inner Eurasia, once the webwork of Alexander's and Genghis' empires, were far from the all-important nodes of contemporary commercial activity, international communication, and personal mobility that are vital to imperial domination. Spykman then turns Mackinder's axiom on its head: "Who controls the Rimland rules Eurasia; Who rules Eurasia controls the destinies of the world." Under Stalin's leadership, Russia may have successfully cocooned itself within multiple layers of protection (Soviet republics, Eastern European and Asian satellites, etc.), but by the 1980s, it was becoming embarrassingly obvious that they had bet on the wrong geopolitician. As the global leader in the development of transnational information and communication networks, the United States had come to dominate the emergent milieu of cyberspace in an imperialistic fashion that can only be compared to Britain's dominance of the high seas in the previous century (Rusciano 2001). A holistic analysis of digital connections to the outside world (bandwidth, Internet hubs, etc.) suggests that the Second World outer rim (the Baltics, Slovenia, the Czech Republic, as well as the cities of Shanghai, Beijing, and Guangzhou) have joined the ICT revolution with gusto, while the inner zones (Mongolia, Transcaspia, and western China) have been left by the wayside.⁵ The American culture industry that has long dominated Western Europe and its Cold War outposts in the eastern Pacific Rim began to steadily penetrate the Iron Curtain during the 1980s, aided by the digitization of information.

⁵ Interestingly, a number of Siberian cities along the trans-Eurasian corridor boast high Internet penetration rates, signalling the advent of "regional ICT metropolises," or alternatively, "nodal outposts" connecting the eastern and western fringes of the virtual Second World.

While Stalin, Khrushchev, Tito, Brezhnev, and Mao might have been able to keep Jesus, jeans, and jazz out of their domains, the new leaders of the Second World found it ever so difficult to maintain prophylaxes against the tiny ones and zeros of the digital age; in the words of Terhi Rantanen, “the first political casualty of the information age was the Communist state system” (2001, 89).

A member of this new generation, Mikhail Gorbachev, belatedly attempted to convert the USSR into an information society. Recognising the crippling effects of the information technology lock-out of his predecessors, Gorbachev included ICT in his plans for *uskorenie* (‘acceleration’) of economic development within the Soviet Union.

Moscow’s twelfth five-year plan of 1985 envisaged 1.3 million PCs [personal computers] in Soviet schoolrooms by 1995. But the Americans already had three million in 1985 and, in any case, the main Soviet PC, the Agat, was an inferior version of the outdated Apple II. Mikhail Gorbachev...was keenly sensitive to these problems. *Informatizatsiya* (crudely, informationization) became the buzzword of his [Gorbachev’s] new era. His American counterpart, Secretary of State George Shultz, played on this concern periodically giving him minatory tutorials about how the rest of the world was moving from “the industrial age to the information age.” At the same time, the communications revolution in phones and faxes, TV and radio, made it even harder to insulate Soviet-bloc citizens from evidence of failure of their regimes and of the lifestyles in the West (Reynolds 2000, 519).

The bell could not be unring. Despite half-hearted attempts to continue repressive policies of technology and information management, KGB surveillance, and ideological control, the virus of opposition spread through Soviet society aided by the radical new technologies of the late 1980s such as audio cassettes, VCR tapes, the personal computer, etc. Whereas Soviet authorities had required typewriters, photocopiers, and other tools for mass production of information to be registered with the government as a firewall against dissident, *samizdat* publications in earlier eras, such policies proved untenable after 1985.

In an idiosyncratic parallel to the invention of the printing press roughly half a millennium earlier, the personal computer and printer gave the individual the ability to produce a nearly limitless amount of documents (Hauben 1997). Such innovation proved to be most threatening to party-controlled regimes which had long enjoyed the benefits of modernity, particularly the power of the state to manage and mobilize the population, the rise of mass politics, taxonomic control over society, and monopolies on time, space, violence, and, of course, the media (Hoffman 2000). Connecting that PC to the burgeoning Internet further allowed transmission of information in ways that Johannes Gutenberg could have never imagined, and ushered in a new era of self-publishing that is still in its early stages. The impacts of new media and novel ICTs were substantially multiplied by the introduction of “socially new” technologies like private phones, which had long eluded the average Soviet citizen (Rantanen 2001).

While Japan, Germany, and the U.S. scrambled to free their workers from the mundane activities that consumed their day in the 1950s and 1960s, Soviet and Eastern European enterprises strived to keep superfluous staff occupied. As Gorbachev introduced *perestroika*, he attempted to streamline industry by dismantling counterproductive bureaucratic structures and encouraging freer flows of ideas within and across Soviet institutions; correspondingly,

ICT slowly became a key measure of this process (MacKenzie 1989). However, as the *New Republic* pointed out in a 1989 article on ICT in the communist bloc communication technologies, “TV is not intrinsically a technology of the individual,” but the personal computer is “fundamentally democratising” (1989, 7). As has been demonstrated by a number of scholars (see Tai 2006; Kalathil and Boas 2003; Woo-Young and Won-Tae 2006), the spread of personal ICTs does have impact on the development of liberal pluralism. Indeed, the leader of Poland’s trade union federation Solidarność (and future president) Lech Wałęsa directly attributes the spread of ICT into his country as an instrumental to success of the democratic movement there (Franda 2002, 100).

In 1989, as part of the increasing widespread policies of *glasnost*, the Soviet Union’s regulation of personal publishing media was finally abandoned as hopelessly difficult in the information age. At the time, U.S. President Ronald Reagan quipped, “Information is the oxygen of the modern age. It seeps through the walls topped by barbed wire, it wafts across the electrified borders.... Technology will make it increasingly difficult for the state to control the information its people receive. The Goliath of totalitarianism will be brought down by the David of the microchip.”⁶ Indeed, information about the West, Stalin’s crimes, and the weakness of the Soviet economy quickly permeated the public sphere, just as the Kremlin had long feared it would if the totalitarian shackles of information control were loosed. The emergence of comparatively free information spaces across Soviet space and Eastern Europe significantly aided the development of a long-stunted civil society and made meaningful coordination with diaspora communities and anti-communist organizations a reality.

The viral-like spread of Tetris from Moscow to Eastern Europe and then to the United States in the second half of the 1980s proved that the flow was not simply a one-way phenomenon (see Karenovics 2007).⁷ However, the build-out of digital networks tended to mirror information flows in the “real world;” as Saskia Sassen puts it, “Digital space, whether public or private, is partly embedded in actual societal structures and power dynamics: its topography weaves in and out of non-electronic space” (2000, 198). While cyberspace provided a vast new reservoir for digital content, the Internet’s ability to impact interpersonal communication remained evolutionary rather than revolutionary until the end of the 1980s. E-mail, as useful as it might be, offered few advantages to the increasingly popular fax machine until the introduction of Internet Relay Chat (IRC). In 1988, Jarkko “WiZ” Oikarinen of Finland’s University of Oulu (sitting on the threshold of the Second World) introduced IRC—a technological platform which allowed geographically distributed users to converse with one another in real time. Bulletin board-type communication was instantly transformed into something much more robust, by allowing users to communicate messages back and forth across incredible distances (and previously salient political boundaries). For those with access to the technology, issues of cost were marginal. IRC demonstrated the emergence of what public intellectual Eugene Volokh has labelled a proliferation of “cheap speech” in cyberspace (c.f.

⁶ Paradoxically, the United States and its Western European allies have enacted significant limitations on free speech in cyberspace since Reagan uttered these prophetic words, including the Communication Decency Act (1996) and French and German suppression of Nazi propaganda on the Web.

⁷ However, the fact that the game, conceived and popularized in the metropole of the Communist Bloc, was “discovered” by the West only after gaining popularity in Budapest (specifically by a Robert Stein, an employee of a British software firm operating in the Hungarian capital) reinforces my subsequent argument that the Second World “core” was, in reality, a peripheral zone in terms of ICT and information transmission.

Cohen 2007, 220). With IRC, the world enjoyed its first “party line” for chatting about a variety of topics from the banal to the esoteric.

The growth of the new platform in its first year was explosive. In the summer of 1989, IRC provided vital channels of unfiltered communication, allowing the outside world to learn about China’s brutal crackdown on the Tiananmen Square protests in record time. The popularity of IRC as a tool for tracking political events in 1989 served as a harbinger of the increasing politicization of cyberspace. In 1991, reports of the hardliner coup d’état against Gorbachev quickly leaked out via IRC. Historian Gladys Ganley contends that the plotters’ critical error in the summer of 1991 was their failure to cut the digital communications links and jam other forms of communication between Moscow and the outside world (1996, 132), while R. Judson Mitchell contends that the “information revolution” of the Gorbachev era had already made impossible the “future operation of the Soviet system as it had functioned since the post-Stalin settlement of 1953-54” (1990, 163). Regardless, the coup failed, the Communist Party abandoned its monopoly on power, and the USSR became a historical entity before the year was out.

Eastern Europe’s (including, on a functional level, the Baltic States’) abandonment of the one-party system in 1989 gave the region a two-year head start on communications infrastructure development. This advantage, when combined with the statist command-and-control legacies of Stalinism, the vast size of post-Soviet space, and Eastern Europe’s comparative proximity to the Western European “technology and information corridor” (see Tanner and Gibbs 1997) which stretches from southeast England to Berlin and Vienna, resulted in significant advances in Central and Eastern Europe and the Baltic Republics (CEE) which were not mirrored in former Soviet Union (FSU) (see [Map 1](#)).⁸ In the decade that followed, the Second World’s seeming ICT homogeneity splintered, as Slovenia and Estonia emerged as digirati nations while Transcaucasia and Central Asia became information deserts. Moscow, and to a lesser extent Leningrad (now renamed St. Petersburg), remained on the information superhighway. Such success stemmed from a new generation of educated elites who moved from the public sector in the business world, making Russia a cheap site for offshore software design, anti-virus programs, and electronic engineering (as well as a poorly-policed redoubt for hackers, crackers, and spammers). However, much of the rest of the FSU suffered through the 1990s with laughably outdated telecommunications infrastructures, poor investment climates, and little political will do anything about either.

⁸ While Estonia, Latvia, and Lithuania are post-Soviet republics, their existence as full-fledged independent states during the interwar period (1918-1939), economic development before and during Soviet rule, and historical ties to the Nordic countries argue for their inclusion in the CEE rather than the FSU category.

Map 1. European Teledensity.

As foreign direct investment (FDI), partnerships with Western European PTTs, and aid from US- and privately-backed philanthropic agencies (Open Society Institute, IREX, USAID, the Eurasian Foundation, etc.) poured into the Baltics, the Visegrád Four (Poland, Hungary, and the Czech and Slovak Republics), and Slovenia, a new class of techno-elite countries was established on the western fringe of the Second World.⁹ It is not coincidental that those countries deemed most ready for admission to the European Community (later the European Union) would benefit the most from the rapid period of investment, reform, and restructuring that followed the seminal political changes of 1989-1991. By the turn of the millennium, this coterie of nations was easily outperforming the rest of the Second World in most per capita

⁹ Originally known as the Visegrád Triangle (before Czechoslovakia's "velvet divorce" in 1993), the group takes its name from a 15 February 1991 summit of the heads of state or government of Czechoslovakia, Hungary and Poland held in the Hungarian castle town of Visegrád. The leaders met to coordinate policies and develop a common strategy for European integration.

ICT metrics, such as Internet hosts, Internet users, personal computers, and teledensity (see [Table 1](#)).

Table 1. ICT in the Second World, 2006 (all figures per 100 residents).

	Mobile Phones	Telephone Mainlines	Personal Computers	Internet Users
Albania	40.0	11.2	1.7	2.4
Armenia	11.0	19.7	6.6	5
Azerbaijan	26.0	14.0	2.3	8
Belarus	42.0	34.6	0.8	35
Bosnia and Herzegovina	41.0	21.6	5.4	21
Bulgaria	80.0	31.2	5.9	28
China, People's Republic of	30.0	28.0	4.3	11
Croatia	67.0	41.3	19	33
Czech Republic	115.0	31.4	24	50
Estonia	107.0	40.4	48	51
Georgia	33.0	12.5	4	4
Hungary	82.0	33.3	15	30
Kazakhstan	33.0	19.1	1.7	2.6
Kyrgyzstan	11.0	8.6	1.9	5
Latvia	81.0	28.7	22	46
Lithuania	128.0	23.3	15	36
Macedonia, Republic of	62.0	21.6	22	19
Moldova	26.0	26.6	2.6	10
Mongolia	22.0	6.1	13	11
North Korea	No data	No data	No data	No data
Poland	76.0	30.1	19	28
Romania	61.0	19.5	11	23
Russia	83.0	28.0	12	17
Serbia and Montenegro	58.0	36.0	4.8	17
Slovakia	84.0	21.7	35	46
Slovenia	88.0	41.7	40	54
Tajikistan	4.0	4.2	0.1	3
Turkmenistan	1.0	8.2	0.7	7.5
Ukraine	37.0	26.4	3.8	11
Uzbekistan	3.0	6.9	3.1	3
Vietnam	12.0	19.1	1.4	18

Source: NationMaster, World Bank, and UNDP.

Interestingly, Poland—one the best performers during the 1990s—has steadily slipped relative to its peers. In 2001, Poland ranked fifth in Internet hosts and Internet users per capita among Second World countries; in 2005, it had dropped to eleventh in both categories, looking more like Romania than its former Visegrád partners. I attribute this decline to what I call

the “city-state effect.” Those states which have structured their economies along the model of a city-state—akin to CEE versions of Singapore or Hong Kong—have proven to be more adept at maintaining strong economic growth, deploying a robust ICT infrastructure, and transitioning towards information-based economies. Smaller countries with primate cities as capitals possess the greatest advantages in this regard. Primate cities are those urban areas which are at least twice as populous as their next largest rival, often containing a quarter or more of the country’s population (see Nagle 2000); for example, both Riga (Latvia) and Tallinn (Estonia) contain over 25% of their country’s respective populations and are the political, economic, and cultural centres of their republics. Other CEE countries (e.g., Bulgaria, Slovenia, Croatia, Hungary and the Czech Republic) possess exemplary primate cities, characterized by high densities of skilled professionals, effective transportation links to other European capitals, and significant economies of scale.¹⁰

Like tiny Latvia and Estonia, these medium-sized European polities have turned themselves into virtual city-states (though ones with sizable hinterlands); nearly all technological development goes on within the immediate environs of the capital, streamlining the process of building out the ICT capacity of the country. As Richard Rosencrance has argued “The Rise of the Virtual State” (1996), the current trend in international political economy is a move away from dependence on “territorially based production capability” and towards an emulation of the “downsized” East Asian tigers; these states’ economies are based on trade, information, finance, and thus “liberated” from geography and the burden of defending and developing far-flung regions. Estonia, Slovenia, Hungary, and the Czech Republic best embody this trend among the CEE polities, while Slovakia, Lithuania, and other small nations are following in their footsteps. However, not all CEE states are on the path to virtuality. Polish fantasies of resurrecting its great power status in the Baltic-Black Sea corridor and Romanian fear of losing its tether on resource-rich, but regionalist Transylvania guarantee that neither Warsaw nor Bucharest will embrace the merits of the “virtual state.” Nor will they be able to turn themselves into city-states like Estonia-Tallinn or Slovenia-Ljubljana. Furthermore, Poland and Romania—the two largest CEE states—are characterized by well-dispersed populations living in multiple, often distant, urban centres. Rather than a single node, these countries must wire several large cities and dozens of medium-sized metropolitan areas.¹¹

In those CEE states which have already joined the European Union, e-governance is also on the rise. As nation-states, both Slovenia and Estonia have emerged pioneers in the field. Estonia was an early adopter of e-banking, e-voting, a “paperless government,” and live streaming of parliament in cyberspace (Drechslera and Ülle 2002). According to the members

¹⁰ While Bratislava effectively functions as a city-state, it is not because of its primate status (Košice is slightly more than 50% as large as the capital). Instead, the Slovakian capital’s proximity to Vienna (less than 60 km) and its placement within the Danubian Corridor drives the city’s development. Slovenia—once the gateway to Yugoslavia—also benefits from its salubrious location in *Mittleuropa*, with Ljubljana functioning as the country’s only city.

¹¹ While Bucharest is technically a primate city (being 70% larger than its closest rival Iași), the largest university in the country and much of Romania’s FDI is located in Transylvania and the Banat regions which border Hungary and the most developed areas of Serbia. Furthermore, Romania has no less than 12 cities with more than 200,000 residents. Warsaw barely meets the definition of a primate city, and Poland has five large cities with more than a half million residents and another dozen medium-sized cities with populations between 200,000 and 500,000. By comparison, Bulgaria and the Czech Republic only have two medium-sized cities, Lithuania and Hungary have one each, and there are none in either Croatia or Slovenia.

of the government, cabinet meeting that once lasted most of the day have been reduced to sessions ranging from 10 minutes to one hour (IMJ 2003). Estonia has also used the Web to extend the welfare state by creating a government-backed site similar to eBay that enables fishermen and other merchants to sell their goods online (Meier 2000). Slovenia made its mark by introducing e-taxes, e-urban planning, and the establishment of direct, digital lines of communication between citizens and the administration (Pinterič 2005). At the municipal level, a number of regional capitals have also scored well. In 2007, a report by the e-Governance Institute at Rutgers University-Newark and the Global e-Policy e-Government Institute at Sungkyunkwan University ranked Prague and Bratislava in the top twenty cities in digital governance (Sofia, Belgrade, Zagreb, Bucharest, and Vilnius all finished in the top forty); Sofia, Riga, and Bratislava were among the top 10 in civic participation via the Internet (Holzer and Kim 2007).

Croatia's isolation from Europe during the quasi-fascist rule of Franjo Tuđman (1990-1999), as well as the difficult years of conflict with Yugoslavia, has naturally stunted the country's growth; however, Croatia has shown marked improvement in recent years and enjoys one of the most developed telecommunications infrastructures in the region due to a long standing dependence on tourism. Zagreb is now posed to move quickly into line with other CEE "information capitals." Serbia (and Montenegro's) isolation from the international community prevented ICT growth during the 1990s, but has not created any permanent impediments to future development. Serbia has more telephone mainlines per capita than almost any other Second World country, though the country still lags in Internet development (see Table 1). However, Belgrade's strong primate position (especially since the secession of Montenegro and Kosovo) and its historic role as the hub of commerce, communication, and transport for the western Balkans portends rapid improvement in the coming years as the country sloughs off the ghosts of the Milošević era. In the southern Balkans, the city-state effect does not aid development (as is the case in much of the FSU, particularly the Caucasus and Central Asia). Tirana and Skopje—while commanding the lion's share of their respective populaces—have failed to take full advantage of their status as primate cities in terms of developing ICT infrastructure and information economies. It should be noted that both are victims of history; Albania was the last holdout of Ottoman suzerainty on the European continent, while Macedonia remained a hotbed of instability and Balkan rivalries during the first half of the twentieth century. Enver Hoxha's autarkic strategy for Albania and Belgrade's miserly underdevelopment of Macedonia (and Albanian Kosovo for that matter) doomed these regions to technological obscurity, making them more like the Caucasus than the CEE.

As one moves from west to east, crossing the interwar border of the Soviet Union, a digital divide becomes increasingly apparent. This divide is not simply one of information "haves" and "have-nots," but a multidimensional phenomenon that encompasses three distinct aspects: a *global divide*, a *social divide* and a *democratic divide* (Norris 2001). While Russia is now tracking well with the CEE countries, nearly all the remaining FSU states are woefully behind their western counterparts in terms of ICT deployment, new media usage, and other measurement of global information integration, clearly exemplifying a global divergence between these two sub-regions of the Second World. Perhaps the most startling manifestation of this divergence is in international Internet bandwidth which strongly favours those countries on the outer rim versus the inner ("Heartland") countries of the Second World

(see [Map 2](#)). On the social front, digital disparities between urban and rural areas, rich and poor, and generational cohorts are all much more sharply drawn in the Commonwealth of Independent States than in Central and Eastern Europe. While these cleavages are certainly perceptible in CEE countries, the penetration of digital culture beyond the confines of the wealthy, young, and urban is dramatic compared to the situation in Ukraine, Russia, and Kazakhstan. Lastly, and perhaps most dramatically, the FSU exhibits a gaping delta when it comes to the democratising aspects of the digital revolution.

Map 2. International Internet Bandwidth across the Second World.

Source: NationMaster.

Whereas Estonian, Slovene and Czech politicians are committed to mobilising the Web to increase transparency and improve communications with their constituents, the past decade has seen the development of “neo-authoritarian” systems that employ subtle controls over the media, cyberspace, and other ICTs (Becker 2004). Within such a system, the most popularly-consumed media platforms (typically television stations) are brought under overt or indirect state control, leaving only print media to function independently. This independence is, however, a hoax; mechanisms of control such as selective prosecution for tax evasion, unpunished crimes against journalists, harsh sentences for “libel” (regardless of the veracity of the printed word), charges of “hooliganism,” government subsidies to “friendly” media voices have forced many newspapers and journals out of business. The end result has been a move towards Internet-based journalism, significantly raising the profile of new media in the FSU. But the government has followed these agents of information freedom even into cyberspace. In Azerbaijan, Internet journalists are detained for their writings, though not officially charged. Much more ominous is the case of Heorhiy Gongadze, a Ukrainian Internet reporter and government critic, who was murdered in 2000, reportedly at the behest of then Ukrainian president Leonid Kuchma (Ivanov 2005).

In addition to physical and economic threats to new media activists, there is also a technology-policy aspect to the issue of ICT in the former Soviet Union. According to Reporters without Borders, three FSU countries rank among their “enemies of the Internet” in 2008: Belarus, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan (two other Second World countries—China and Vietnam—also make the list). While Turkmenistan under Saparmurat Niyazov (Turkmenbashi) was described as an “Internet black hole” that extensively blocked and filtered Internet content, most post-Soviet dictators pursue a more sophisticated policy towards information and communications technologies. In these republics, the government officially lauds Internet usage, but employs an iron fist against violators of these countries’ Byzantine regulations of ICTs. Shanthi Kalathil refers to this phenomenon as “Authoritarianism 2.0.”

Forced to choose between jumping on the information superhighway or languishing on the unwired byways of technology, many authoritarian regimes are choosing to go along for the Internet ride. In addition to helping autocratic rulers compete in the global economy, the Internet and other information and communication technologies (ICTs) can streamline authoritarian states and help them govern more effectively.... hardheaded autocrats aren’t suddenly soliciting e-mail advice from dissenters. Controlling information has always been a cornerstone of authoritarian rule, and leaders are naturally suspicious of the Web (Kalathil 2003, 43).

As post-Soviet regimes embrace this misbegotten form of e-governance, they gain the ability to counteract actions of grassroots, digitally-based movements, what Marcus Franda (2002) refers to as the *publicum* of cyberspace. In recent years, a number of successful strategies for dampening popular, Web-based discontent have emerged. Belarus is the paragon of this strategy.

In public speeches, President Alexander Lukashenko has stressed that in modern society much depends on successful information and knowledge management. He has promised free access to governmental information resources in an effort to fight corruption and inefficiency of state administrative institutions (Doroshevich 2003). However, the state-owned telecommunications company Beltelecom, which manages all of the country’s Internet servers, reportedly blocked access to opposition or independent websites and monitored Internet communications during the 2006 presidential election period (Freedom House 2007). The government’s campaign was well-prepared for an e-insurgency by US- and Polish-backed NGOs bent on removing Lukashenko from office in what was marketed in the West as an inevitable fourth “colour revolution.” While democratic activists came armed with their mobile phones ready to repeat the SMS-based coordination that characterized the Orange Revolution of 2004-05, Lukashenko’s techno-authoritarianism prevented his enemies from effectively mobilising. In fact, Minsk’s employment of new media technology was not confined to the home front. During the immediate aftermath of the rigged election, Radio Free Europe/Radio Liberty—one of the few external sources of news in Belarus—saw its servers targeted in cyber-attacks. A similar wave of attacks came again in 2008 in advance of a planned opposition protest (Macdonald 2008). More recently, a new law dictates that all Internet sites originating in the country must be registered with the government.

The methodologies employed in the Central Asia Republics (CARs) can be divided into two categories: the first utilizes a Belarusian-style scheme of state control over electronic media and ICT platforms, while the second mirrors the Russian system (discussed in detail later) of monitoring, mediating, and—when deemed necessary—disrupting content. This divergence in policy stems from the predominant funding sources for ICT deployment (McGlinchey and Johnson 2007). In war-ravaged Tajikistan and resource-poor Kyrgyzstan, Western governments and international NGOs provide much of the investment in new technologies, and as a result they exert at least marginal influence over policy. Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan, countries with substantial natural resources, are less constrained by foreign forces. According to Eric McGlinchey and Erica Johnson, “Paradoxically, at least in the Central Asia cases, it is poverty rather than wealth that leads to a more competitive, vibrant, and free telecommunications and electronic media environment” (2007, 285).

Kazakhstan, the world’s ninth largest country with a population of barely 15 million, represents the ambiguities of the Internet in Central Asia. President Nursultan Nazarbayev hopes to turn his country into the central axis of a “new Silk Road” linking Europe, China, and the Indian subcontinent, while simultaneously investing the republic’s oil wealth in a Norwegian-style development program to develop an information society for the future. IT deployment is central to this plan; however, hundreds of laws are applied to Internet activity (many of which apply Sovietesque definitions of “state secrets” to even the most innocuous bits of data) and the public network is monopolized by Kazakhtelecom, which engages in both filtering and monitoring of Internet transmissions (Deibert *et al.* 2008). While seemingly trivial, the recent “battle over Borat”—the mass-mediated feud between British comedian Sacha Baron Cohen and Astana—evinced the intense politicization of Kazakhstan’s cyberspace when KazNIC, the country’s administrator for domain names, removed Baron Cohen’s site from the country’s servers, referring to the issue as a “political matter,” though the organization’s spokesperson could not say who was behind the decision (Saunders 2008, 103). The *International Herald Tribune* indicated that the association received complaints from both the government and President Nazarbayev’s personal security service, which accused the borat.kz web site of impugning the “international image of Kazakhstan” and that the site was registered by a non-resident of the country intent on “unconscientious usage” (see Saunders 2007).

In comparison to Uzbekistan, however, Kazakhstan appears nothing short of benevolent. According to Ronald Deibert, the director of Citizen Lab, an Internet freedom watchdog, “Uzbekistan is the undisputed leader in applying Internet controls...the government employs sophisticated multilayered mechanisms to exercise control over the Internet, including adopting restrictive policies, applying technological measures, and compelling self-censorship on the media” (Deibert *et al.* 2008, 409). Fearful of the spread of the Web-savvy, transnational Islamist party Hizb ut-Tahrir (<http://www.hizbuttahrir.org/>), President Islam Karimov has turned the full force of his police state against the underground network of desktop publishers who connect to the Web to download HT’s daily messages and then distribute them under doors of the faithful as *shabnamas* (‘night letters’) (Escobar 2005). In the wake of the Andijan Uprising in 2005, Karimov’s paranoia reached a fever pitch: numerous Internet cafés in Tashkent and other cities were shuttered after failing to receive government approval to operate (Lyons 2006) and the government began issuing steep fines for visiting news sites such as

Fergana.ru and Centrasia.org (Kudriashov 2005). Such cyber-phobia is ironic given that is Uzbekistan was, as late as 2001, listed as a “regional leader in the adoption of the Internet and the prioritization of ICTs as a mechanism for national development” (Deibert *et al.* 2008, 409).

Even in the most liberal country in the region, Kyrgyzstan, frequently described as an “island of democracy,” cyberspace has emerged as a site of creeping neo-authoritarianism, typically in response to aggressive anti-government campaign by opposition forces. In the early days of the “Tulip Revolution” which toppled President Askar Akayev, a mysterious “black PR” e-mail campaign ravaged Kyrgyz cyberspace. This political spam consisted of “messages aimed at discrediting the opposition being sent from ‘spoofed,’ or falsified, e-mail addresses supposedly belonging to legitimate independent Internet domains such as Gazeta.kg and CentrAsia.ru... Many of the messages launched personal attacks on opposition leaders...[who] were variously portrayed as Western-funded agents, self-interested money-grabbers, printers of counterfeit money, and communist-era politicians intent on deceiving people for their own gain” (Wilkinson 2005). The barrage of e-mails was quickly followed by denial of service (DoS) attacks on opposition servers. While some of the attacks, such as the one against the youth movement KelKel (“Renaissance”) were the work of the government, most of the attacks were led by sympathetic non-government organizations and/or individuals—a practice that characterized the 2007 pro-Russian DoS attacks on Estonian Web sites and servers in response to Tallinn’s decision to relocate the Bronze Soldier statue to the edge of the capital.

Unlike their post-Soviet counterparts in the old periphery of the USSR, Russians have joined the information revolution with zeal and the Internet is making an impact on contemporary Russian society. For Internet users in Russia, the Internet’s capacity to provide unfiltered access to information and news was a driving force in adoption. As Henrike Schmidt and Katy Teubener state, “The Internet in Russia developed within a period of overall social, political and economic transformation” (Schmidt 2006, 14). As such, the Internet was initially viewed as a truly “new medium,” in that its proliferation occurred after the collapse of the Soviet system which had manipulated previous media platforms such as television, film, and newspapers (all of which were stained by the legacy of Soviet totalitarianism). In recent years, Russia has significantly improved its position within the Second World. The increasing prosperity of Russians—buoyed by rising oil and gas prices and Putin’s comparatively sound management of the economy—is aiding Internet adoption levels. Russia’s changing demographics, specifically the movement of young people to the cities, further promotes Internet use through work, home access, or Internet cafés. The increasing convergence of mobile telephony and Internet access is also promoting greater levels of Russian web use. This trend is also attributable to ICT-related investor enthusiasm for Vladimir Putin, who immediately demonstrated an “avid interest in the Internet” and, somewhat ominously, a more aggressive information technology policy including his “information security doctrine” (Franda 2002, 111-112).

Wireless telephony and Internet access via mobile phones has been especially rapid. This is in some part due to the retarded state of Soviet Russia’s landline telephony network which was chronically neglected by the state (Rantanen 2001). While the number of private fixed-line telephones rose by more than 50% during the Yeltsin years, the growth has slowed in the

current decade. In 2006, Russia had only reached thirty fixed lines per 100. The urban-rural divide is marked: 97% of Muscovites have a telephone at home, while the percentage of their countrymen possessing a home phone is less than half (EIU 2008, 25). The sluggish rate of landline build-outs has benefited the mobile phone industry. Today, Russia's mobile telephony penetration is in excess of 100%, with approximately 170 million subscribers (EIU 2008). While Russia's national Internet penetration rate remain mired in the "mushy middle" of all countries worldwide (ranking eighty-three out of 200 in 2005), the level of growth is quite robust, rising from 16% in 2005 to 27% in 2008. In early 2008, Russia's Information and Communications Ministry estimated that more than half of the country's citizens would be online by 2010. Recently, the number of Russian Internet domains reached 500,000, with .ru now being the second-fastest growing domain on the net after China's (RIA Novosti 2006). Furthermore, e-commerce in Russia reached \$4.47 billion in 2005 (Novecon 2006); Russia outpaced its western counterparts in e-commerce growth in 2006 with a 42% jump compared to a 25% rise in among European states (Yandex 2007). When looking at Russia through the lens of its major metropolitan areas (Moscow and St. Petersburg), the country is extremely well-wired. According to a recent report, more than 55% of Muscovites (5.7 million) access the Internet, and one-quarter of those do so via mobile phone (BBC 2008). Plans for a city-wide WiFi network were recently announced for the Russian capital—a move which sharply increase the number of Russian Web users by providing access to nearly 4 million households in the capital.

While use of the Internet has skyrocketed under Putin's watch, so has government eavesdropping and laws directed at Internet users (such as restrictions against the loosely defined crime of "extremist content"). In post-Soviet Russia, the Internet has gone from a novelty to part of the regime's ever-growing "participatory panopticon" (Dennis 2008) based on resurgent Russian nationalism and a desire to protect the nation from enemies within and without. Since Putin came to power in 2000, the Kremlin has cracked down on the country's freedom of the press and nationalized all television stations. While radio and print media have not suffered to the extent that TV has, radio broadcasters and newspaper editors are under constant pressure to toe the governmental line. Internet-based news and information sources, however, operate in a relatively free environment (though intimidation remains a major issue). As such, recent surveys show that the Internet is displacing newspapers as the primary source of news among the educated, high-income elites, and youth (Pietilainen 2008). While Moscow has made tentative moves towards policing the Internet, such efforts are currently producing little to no impact on the freedom of information in Russian cyberspace (Strukov 2006).

Even if the Kremlin attempted something analogous to the "Great Firewall of China" to block access to certain sites, the government is woefully unprepared to implement or enforce such measures at the current time. What has proved more successful, however, is what Kingsley Dennis (2008) calls "virtual vigilantism" or "sousveillance." Non-state (or, more likely, state-supported) actors scour Russian cyberspace for "anti-Russian" users and content and then engage in Internet attacks against them. In her paper "Semantic Guerrilla War in RuNet" (2006), Dyakova outlined the propensity for nationalist "flash mobs" in Russian cyberspace whereby any perceived threat to the nation is met with an overwhelming digital response by supporters of Russia. The international corollary to this form of vigilantism has manifested in attacks against Estonian, Georgian, and other ICT infrastructures in response to

real or perceived slights against the Russian Federation, its citizens, and/or its “countrymen” (ethnic Russians and Russophones living in the near abroad). As such, cyberspace and Russia’s ICT infrastructure are being employed on both the state and non-state level as tool of the country’s geopolitical power.

It is important to note that the RuNet is not confined to Russia’s territorial geography (as evidence by the URLs of some the sites mentioned above). It is also deeply embedded in the near abroad, i.e., the fourteen other former Soviet republics. Expatriate Russians, specifically those Russians who were beached by the Soviet Union’s ebbing borders in 1991, have acute reasons for utilising the Internet for news and information. Since independence, the Newly Independent States of Eurasia have all, to varying degrees, reduced the role of the Russian language in print, radio, and television media. Whereas it was once the standard that all media were dominated by the Russian language, today the titular languages reign supreme in most of the former Soviet republics, although in certain areas such as eastern Ukraine and northern Kazakhstan, Russian remains the dominant idiom of traditional forms of mass media (Laitin 1998). Such circumscription mirrors similar efforts to promote the titular languages in the political, scientific, and educational milieus. For Russians living in the near abroad, the war of attrition on the Russian language has been viewed as a political—rather than cultural—move intended to artificially promote the interests of the titular majority at their expense. However in the RuNet, Russians are able to make themselves at home (Saunders 2006).¹² In addition to ethnic Russians, a generation of elapsed cultural Russians, i.e., *homo post-Sovietici*, are also drawn to the RuNet. Russian is the dominant language of Internet use in Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, and a number of other CARs. Due to the robustness of Russian-language cyberspace, Russophones from all over the FSU choose to spend their cyber-time in the RuNet rather than their indigenous cyberspaces.

While the imagined geography of the RuNet extends from two great nodes (Moscow and St. Petersburg) into ever thinner tendrils connecting the network to the Russian countryside and diasporic outposts around the world, Chinese cyberspace—arguably the most dynamic and important of the Second World digital networks—does not at all resemble an imperial hub-and-spoke model that characterizes the contemporary RuNet.¹³ Instead, Chinese Internet space is a loose confederal nebula populated by millions of overseas Chinese (residing in the Canada, the U.S., Southeast Asia, and other parts of the Pacific Rim), residents of the comparatively liberal Internet zones of Taiwan and Hong Kong, citizens of the PRC, and “official” representatives of the government in Beijing. The Chinese Web is thus a curious combination of “central planning” (à la Marxism-Leninism) and unseen—and often unpredictable—transnational market forces.

¹² Cyberspace is not a simple broadcast medium like television or radio; instead, it is a new form of all-enveloping media (that is, multiple, often simultaneous conduits of transmission) in which one can escape what is going on in the world rather than embrace it. As such, it is not surprising that William Gibson, in his discussion of cyberspace, often used the concept of the *matrix*, “a word that finds its etymology in ‘womb’—the paradigmatic topos of container and contained” (Myers 2001, 893).

¹³ It should be noted that Russian cyberspace started out as an environment dominated by members of the “old diaspora” of Russians in Western Europe and North America; however, this is now changing. Where the bulk of RuNet traffic once originated in the US, Germany, and Israel, such activity now accounts for only about 10% of all RuNet traffic (Schmidt, Teubener, and Zurawski 2006, 125–6).

China's—and the Chinese'—attempt to master the current ICT revolution is not only an economic issue, but also a geopolitical one. Interestingly, while most diasporic Russians remain lukewarm about the reassertion of Russian power in Eurasia, overseas Chinese are often more nationalistic than their mainland counterparts (Saunders and Ding 2006). Since the country's first connection to the Internet in 1993, Beijing has used informatization as lever to pry China out of the ranks of the Third World. As Deng Xiaoping abandoned Mao's "vertical control" of ICT and media as a "conveyor belt carrying party thought from the leaders top the masses," China experienced the most rapid telecommunications build-out in history (Kalathil and Boas 2003, 18-19). As the largest single nation in cyberspace, ethnic Chinese are well-positioned along the digital terrains that mirror (and sustain) the pathways of global commerce, and can exert substantive influence over the future development of the Internet.¹⁴ While China is (in)famous for its policing of the Internet, particularly the possibly apocryphal claims that some 30,000 cyber-police are "always watching" (MacLeod 2006) and blocking access to political sites, the evolution of a digitally-networked elite in the country is resulting in a flourishing civil society, something virtually unknown over the past century (Tai 2006). Unlike Russia where virtual vigilantism seems to only buttress the governing elite, China's "smart mobs" are as equally prone to nationalist vitriol as they are to condemning local officials for corruption, exposing police brutality, and investigating cover-ups related to SARS. Strangely complementing this situation, China—unlike Russia which favours the radical cyber-right over the reformist digerati left—polices its netizens on both ends of the political spectrum, punishing reactionary Marxist-Leninists as well as Tibetan and Taiwanese "splitists" and Falun Gong "cultists" (Kalathil and Boas 2003).

From a geopolitical perspective, it is interesting to note the lingering impact of imperialism and Cold War-era politico-economic linkages on China's "Internet miracle." As discussed earlier, the PRC's ICT deployment mirrored its economic liberalization and engagement with the global economy. The fact that the maritime provinces of Guangdong, Fujian, and Zhejiang and the city-states of Shanghai and Beijing dominate China's rise to the world status of an economic powerhouse is closely tied to these regions' ICT interconnections with the global information superhighway.¹⁵ A map of the world's data traffic flows is uncannily similar to that of late nineteenth century shipping lanes, with intense traffic flowing across the Pacific, connecting Seattle, San Francisco, and Los Angeles to Tokyo, Seoul, Taipei, Hong Kong, and Singapore (see [Map 3](#)). From this geopolitical perspective, the cities of China's southern coast present an Asia complement to the Baltic "information capitals" of Tallinn, Riga, and Vilnius, while Beijing and Shanghai mirror the CEE data hubs of Prague and Budapest. Unlike Russia, a country hemmed in by physical geography and its own legacy of creating a Mackinderesque *cordon sanitaire*,¹⁶ China resides at the core edge of the world

¹⁴ Ethnic Chinese represent majorities in four states (PRC, Taiwan, Singapore, and Hong Kong) and significant minorities in another 20 countries.

¹⁵ Although it should be noted that China, unlike many FSU countries, is strongly committed to winnowing its domestic digital divide; according to Kalathil and Boas, "At various levels of government, innovative initiatives are being taken to improve rural life though the use of ICTs" (2003: 24). This is particularly true in the "Heartland" zones of China's far west.

¹⁶ While the original *cordon sanitaire* was imposed by the victors of the Great War to keep Soviet Russia's influence at bay in the east, Stalin inverted the structure after World War II to protect the Russian core of the Second World from Western, "imperialist" influence.

network. Sitting on its borders or within the country's sphere of influence are a host of countries (Japan, South Korea, Singapore, Vietnam, Taiwan, etc.) that are inextricably bound to China's economic fate. Russia, however, is walled off from the core of the global network by a belt of states on its western fringe, many of which view Moscow with a mix of suspicion and derision.

Map 3. Map of Major International Internet Routes.

Source: TeleGeography Research.

In conclusion, the century-long process of wiring the Second World, and, more importantly, the last 15 years of breakneck ICT deployment have been an uneven affair. Influenced by a paradoxical combination of totalitarianism, post-Cold War stratagems, and path-dependent commercial links that defy politics, the western and eastern fringe of the Second World have enjoyed rapid growth in the realm of ICT infrastructure. Thus, the global ICT “Rimland” (maritime China, the Baltic States, and the European CEE states) wield considerable cyber-muscle, while the digitally-challenged “Heartland” (Transcaucasia, the ‘Stans, Russia’s Eurasian core, and western China) leaves much to be desired in terms of teledensity, Internet penetration, and use of new media. Russia—and more to the point the once (and perhaps future) imperial centre, Moscow—commands a respectable position among of the world’s wired nations, yet one which is discomfiting to many given the USSR’s technological and industrial dominance only a few decades ago. The meteoric rise of the Asian Tigers, Ireland, and Israel from quasi-Third World status to the ranks of the First World on the backs of their information technology industries suggest that small, littoral city-state-like nations are more adept at converting the digital revolution into economic success. By contrast, larger states, particularly those with extensive rural hinterlands—such as India—have seen development manifest much more un-

evenly. Other countries, like the Democratic Republic of Congo and Burma, have failed altogether to benefit from the systemic changes in the global communications and information network. Such technological diversity is echoed in the Second World, from über-wired Slovenia to Russia's motley mix of digital haves and have-nots to the Internet black hole that is North Korea. As the Second World continues to grapple with challenges of post-totalitarianism, ICT and new media will remain a bellwether of societal transition; however, we must not forget that geopolitics as well as history, culture, and socio-economic factors, have predetermined much of this success or failure.

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